

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10904609>

TEACHING TERMS TO CADETS IN CLASSES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Mengliyeva S.S

Teacher of the department “Learning languages”
of the University of Public Safety
of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Annotation: *teaching terms means making the primary focus on helping cadets acquire terminology of special profession. In English language teaching methods are systems for structuring lessons while approaches are less concerned with how the lesson is structured and more concerned with the general focus of instruction. This article deals with the notion of lexical skills, structure, qualities, stable conditions for the formation of lexical skills, as well as steps that passes every new lexical unit. All this must be taken into account in the process of learning a foreign language vocabulary.*

Keywords: *lexical skills, teaching materials, foreign language teaching, methodical classification.*

ОБУЧЕНИЕ ТЕРМИНАМ КУРСАНТОВ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКАМ

Аннотация: *В современной образовательной сфере внимание уделяется улучшению качества образовательного процесса и эффективности преподавания иностранных языков. Статья рассматривает развитие методики и дидактики, лингвистики и психологии в контексте обучения иностранным языкам, акцентируя внимание на проблемах запоминания терминологии и развития лексических навыков. Представлены различные упражнения для формирования и укрепления лексического запаса, включая имитационные, трансформационные и коммуникативные задания. Особое внимание уделено важности визуального и аудиального восприятия слов, а также необходимости практического применения новой лексики в условиях общения.*

Ключевые слова: *лексические навыки, учебные материалы, обучение иностранному языку, методическая классификация.*

At the present stage of education the development of educational institution is focused on improving the quality of the whole educational process and the effectiveness of foreign language teaching. Throughout the XX century, such science as the methodology and didactics, linguistics and psychology were focused on addressing the range of interrelated problems; the main one is the problem of learning a foreign language by learners of different ages and levels of education. One of the important methods of educational problems is the problem of learning terminology. Mastering terminology is a specific process, as some expressions and words are memorized better but for getting the others it is necessary to do special exercises which are aimed at improving the process of remembering. Practice of cadets in mastering new words is realized with the help of exercises, directed on formation of lexical productive skill and its improvement. All exercises in connection with its structure can be divided into two categories: exercises that focused on memorizing the words, their semantics in unity with phonetic and grammatical form, which results in the selection of words from long-term memory, and exercises the purpose of which is to strengthen the syntagmatic and paradigmatic relations of lexical units. As the word (its form and meaning) is absorbed through situational relatedness and the need for expressing thoughts and feelings, initial training in the use of new vocabulary after the presentation is done in conditional-speech exercises (exercises in imitation, substitution, transformation, reproduction), performed in conditions of a specially organized interaction. These exercises are accompanied by communicative unit. Training in simulation allows learners to create sensations through auditory and visual image of the word, which is associated with speech motor that provides durability memorization of formal characteristics of speech. No less important, according to Filatov V.M., is that there is an awareness of the importance and purpose of the words in their unity, on the one hand, and the association of the word (the auditory image) with purpose. Wildcard exercises help to strengthen these ties and develop associative action of calling words. According to communicative and practical purpose of teaching foreign languages in the high school the variety of exercises can be reduced to three language types: 1. Non-communicative exercises – this type of exercises performed for the purpose of comprehension and the conscious assimilation of linguistic material (grammar, lexical, phonetic) in different types of speech activity. This includes the following exercises: 1) language or aspect: a) grammar (for example: setting the verb in the correct form); b) lexical (for example: substitution of suitable the meaning of the words, grouping words according to topics); c) phonetic (for example: reading the number words, grouping words according to the way of pronouncing). This type of exercises at the relevant stage of learning material is used as a part of homework: 2) transformational exercises (for example: modification

of the affirmative sentences into interrogative, active to passive form); 3) exercises in translation (this type of exercise is used as a control); 4) imitative, wildcard exercises – the principle of operation is that the pupil expands lexical unit in a given structure or make sentences from the words given in the different columns. 2. Speech exercises or communicative exercises The purpose of these exercises is the implementation of the communicative functions of foreign language and teaching communicative skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing). Speech exercises – are always creative exercises. They are always speech thoughtful tasks of different levels. The main characteristic of exercises – are pragmatism and motivation (providing initiative, motivation of students). Passov E.I and Kuznetsova E.E. organize these exercises into three groups: 1) exercises of rendering the content: a retelling, short selective essay, retelling -translation, dramatization and other types of exercises; 2) description exercises: the description of elementary images, feature stories, real objects; 3) exercises of expression, the expression of attitudes and evaluations: discussion, comments. A special kind of exercises - exercises simulating communication, allowing to work in a fast pace, simple from the psychological point of view. By nature, they can be verbal; in methodological orientation. Examples: statement exercises, conditional conversation, students' questions, press conferences, interviews, exercises such as "contact me". 3. Conditional-speech exercises or conditionally communicative exercises. The characteristic feature of this type of exercises is that it allows practicing language material in educational or conditional communication that simulates naturally. Conditional-speech exercises should be situational (any remark of the teacher and the student's answer must be relevant to the situation, relationship of the partners, their activities). They must ensure that the students focus on the purpose and content of the statements, not on the form, they characterized by the communicative value of the phrase, as they are learning. The teacher should avoid flimsy remarks of the type "Tell me, that you are doing the same thing: - I wear a coat in the winter. And in the winter I wear a coat". It should be born in mind the efficiency of the exercises in time. Types of conditional-speech exercises: imitative - student completely imitates teacher's remark; substitution - in these exercises a substitution of lexical units is taken in a receiving structure; transformation - the transformation of perceived forms (for example, transfer the passive voice to active); reproduction - self-perception suggests assimilated form. According to the other type of classification lexical exercises can be distinguished: 1) By type of speech activity, which includes the word - reproductive and productive. 2) By mastering the words, i.e., on the stages of development of lexical skills. 3) In the direction of lexical exercises on certain aspects - phonetic, graphic, etc. 4) In the direction of exercises to create a certain type of speech communication. 5)

How the exercise involves working with an isolated word, or the word in the phrase or sentence 6) By the type of operations conducted to study the Word (replacement, insertion, etc.). 7) Focus on vocabulary exercises to learn new words or to repeat words. Non-contextual exercises can be as follows: learning; nomination of items; grouping words according to certain characteristics; the translation of individual words from one language to another. Monologue speech exercises are: commenting on a series of paintings with the use of studied words; composing monologue to a series of drawings, film; to compare the content of two texts; record on topic; preparation of a report on the topic; explanation of events. Dialogic exercises include: the use of studied vocabulary in the students' questions to the text; answer the teacher's questions in word or in combination; preparation of micro-dialogues of various types with the use of studied words; preparation of dialogues for typical situations; a series of questions to guess the conceived word. Ways to practice vocabulary items. "Listen and repeat" is important because we know that confidently pronouncing a word indicates that it will be stored well. Other simple activities include matching (words to definitions, synonyms to antonyms), fill in the blank, pictures representing the vocabulary item, "make up a sentence using new words" and crossword puzzles. Total Physical Response (TPR) is an excellent way to introduce actions (that is, verbs). Games like "Simon Says" and "Jeopardy" are adaptable to vocabulary learning. Asking students to invent dialogues or skits where they use as many vocabulary words as possible allows students to be creative and allows them to use the words in realistic contexts (be sure to give feedback to students). Any sentence can be called as lexical exercise where the learner focuses on teaching vocabulary. The system of lexical exercises involves the concept of teaching vocabulary. The system of lexical exercises – is the general description of the process of vocabulary teaching. The basis for the formation lexical skills has certain laws, principles, and keeping them is a necessary condition for the efficiency of the learning process. These include didactic principles such as: visibility, activity, durability, consistency, awareness, scientific, age-appropriate and methodical: communicative orientation of education, temporality, collective interaction, life orientation training. There are also private methodological principles in the work on vocabulary: the gradual formation of skill, the adequacy of the exercises generated by the action, interaction exercises on the formation of lexical, grammatical, phonetic speech of the parties, taking into account the interactions of oral forms, testing of vocabulary with the development of reading and writing, the interaction of all kinds of speech activity.

REFERENCES:

1. Nasirova, Saodat. "Staff of officials of the Eastern Palace in ancient China." *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities* 12 (2022): 19-22.
2. Nasirova, Saodat A. "Principles for translating vocabulary with background information." *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies* 2.07 (2022): 82-87.
3. NASIROVA, SAODAT. "Human resource system of ancient China (chronological aspect)." *SHARQ MASH'ALI* 01 (2022): 31-32.
4. Nasirova, Saodat Abdullaevna. "Лексико-Семантический Анализ Общественно–Политических Терминов Древнего Китайского Языка: Система Кадровых Ресурсов." *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities* 17 (2023): 20-30.
5. Намозова, Дилноза Бердимуротовна. "Peculiarities of phonetic competence development in conditions of artificial multilingualism." *инновации в педагогике и психологии* 4.1 (2021).
6. Namozova, D. B., and M. X. Rashidova. "PHONETIC COMPETENCE IN CONDITIONS OF ARTIFICIAL MULTILINGUALISM. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2 (19), 301–305." (2023).
7. Mengliyeva, S. "MA'LUM SOHAGA OID TERMINLARNING LINGVISTIK O 'ZIGA XOSLIGI." *TADQIQOTLAR* 26.1 (2023): 27-33.
8. Musayeva, Sh I., and S. S. Mengliyeva. "Kursantlarning madaniyatlararo muloqot kompetensiyasini ingliz tilini o 'qitish orqali rivojlantirish." *Инновационные исследования в науке* 1.14 (2022): 144-148.
9. Mengliyeva, S. "SOHAVIY TERMINLARNING LISONIY XUSUSIYATLARI." *Innovative Development in Educational Activities* 2.19 (2023): 293-300.
10. Mengliyeva, S. S. "INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA HARBIY TERMINLARNI O 'QITISH." *Ta'lim fidoyilari* (2022): 246-250.
11. Mengliyeva, S. S. "INGLIZ TILI DARSIDA HARBIY TERMINLARNI OQITISH." *Ta'lim fidoyilari* Special issue (2022): 246-250.
12. Kenjabayevna, Darvishova Gulchehra. "DESCRIPTION OF GENDER ISSUES IN THE NOVELS OF CHARLOTTE BRONTE." *TADQIQOTLAR* 26.1 (2023): 18-21.
13. Darvishova, Gulchehra Kenjabayevna. "THE REPRESENTATION OF PATRIARCHAL IDEOLOGY AND GENDER ROLES IN CHARLOTTE

- BRONTE'S LITERATURE." *Innovative Development in Educational Activities* 3.4 (2024): 245-249.
14. Darvishova, Gulchehra Kenjabayevna. "THE IMPORTANCE OF EQUALITY OF WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN THE WORKS OF CHARLOTTE BRONTE." *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences* 4.1 (2024): 345-352.
15. Булычёва, Маргарита Фаритовна, and Халида Абдхамидовна Валиева. "Принципы и правила проведения занятия в малых группах на примере военного вуза." *Наука и образование сегодня* 12 (47) (2019): 72-74.
16. Булычёва, М. Ф. "К ВОПРОСУ О ЭФФЕКТИВНЫХ СТРАТЕГИЯХ КОММУНИКАЦИИ." *Educational Research in Universal Sciences* 2.4 (2023): 535-539.
17. Булычёва, Маргарита Фаритовна, and Динара Талатовна Зайнутдинова. "К вопросу о методических рекомендациях по работе с авторской песней." *Science and Education* 4.3 (2023): 735-747.
18. Bulichyova, Margarita. "METHODODOLOGICAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR WORKING WITH AUTHOR'S SONG." *Modern Science and Research* 2.3 (2023): 256-260.
19. Булычёва, М. Ф. "ЧЕТЫРЕ ПАРАМЕТРА КОММУНИКАЦИИ." *ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ИЛМИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР: ДАВРИЙ АНЖУМАНЛАР: 10-ҚИСМ* 42.
20. Булычева, Маргарита, and Дауылбай Жайлаубаевич Курбанбаев. "АКТУАЛЬНОСТЬ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ СТО ДЛЯ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ СПОСОБОВ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕРРИТОРИАЛЬНОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬЮ ВОИНСКИХ ЧАСТЕЙ." *Innovative Development in Educational Activities* 2.7 (2023): 116-134.
21. Курбанбаев, Дауылбай Жайлаубаевич, and Маргарита Фаритовна Булычева. "К ВОПРОСУ О ЗАРУБЕЖНЫХ МАГНИТОМЕТРИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВАХ ОБНАРУЖЕНИЯ." *Educational Research in Universal Sciences* 2.3 (2023): 507-529.
22. Зайнутдинова, Д. Т., and М. Ф. Булычёва. "Эффективность применения в образовании информационно-коммуникационных технологий." *Технологии обучения русскому языку как иностранному и диагностика речевого развития*. 2022.
23. Булычёва, М. Ф. "МЕТОД ПРОЕКТНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА." *Материалы Международной научно-практической онлайн конференции «Современные технологии в преподавании языков в*

- дистанционном формате: международный опыт проблемы и перспективы» включают доклады и выступления участников конференции–доцентов, исследователей, педагогов с большим стажем.
24. Egamberdieva, G. M. "Funkcii epitetov v «Lesnoj kapeli» MM Prishvina. XIV VINOGRADOVSKIE CHTENIYA (Tashkent, 16 maya 2018 goda). Sbornik nauchnyh trudov Mezhdunarodnoj nauchno-prakticheskoy konferencii.– Ekaterinburg: Ural'skij gosudarstvennyj ekonomicheskij universitet. 2018.–S. 101-104." *XVI Виноградовские чтения.-Екатеринбург-Ташкент (2020):* 135-138.
 25. Эгамбердиева, Г. М. "О хорезмских сказках, записанных АН Самойловичем." *Polish Journal of Science* 36-2 (2021): 52-54.
 26. Рашидова, Мунаввар Хайдаровна. "Теория "Зона ближайшего развития" ЛС Выгодского и технология скаффолдинг как основные понятия лингвометодической поддержки в обучении курсантов английскому языку." *Science and Education* 4.1 (2023): 688-695.
 27. Рашидова, Мунаввар Хайдаровна. "О некоторых аспектах коммуникативной компетенции." *ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА МИЛЛИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР: ДАВРИЙ АНЖУМАНЛАР: 10-ҚИСМ*: 64.
 28. Рашидова, Мунаввар Хайдаровна. "ИСТОРИЯ СКАФФОЛДИНГА И ТЕОРИЯ "ЗОНЫ БЛИЖАЙШЕГО РАЗВИТИЯ". " *Innovative Development in Educational Activities* 2.11 (2023): 487-491.
 29. Rashidova, Munavvar Haydarovna, and Dilnoza Berdimurotovna Namozova. "DEVELOPING B1 LEVEL EFL LEARNERS'SPEAKING SKILLS THROUGH GAMES." *Innovative Development in Educational Activities* 3.4 (2024): 226-231.
 30. Рашидова, Мунаввар Хайдаровна, and Дилноза Бердимуротовна Намозова. "КОММУНИКАТИВНАЯ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКАМ." *TADQIQOTLAR* 26.1 (2023): 34-38.